

Ethno-political Violence and Everyday Life

A Case Study of PECHS, Karachi

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Formal Declaration

I hereby, declare that I have produced the present work by myself and without any aid other than those mentioned herein. Any ideas taken directly or indirectly from third party sources are indicated as such.

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Islamabad, 06 June 2016

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This is to certify that we have read the thesis submitted by Miss. Shehla Ghafoor. It is our judgment that this thesis is of sufficient standard to warrant its acceptance by Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad for the award of the degree of “MSc in Anthropology”.

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Dedication

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Abstract

This study is based on the effects of ethno-political violence on everyday life of the citizens of Karachi, with a particular focus on the vicinity of Pakistan Employees Cooperative Housing Society or PECHS. The study examines the mindset of the people being affected by ethno-political violence on a daily basis with an emphasis on the coping mechanisms used by the residents along with an insight into the cultural repercussions that this ethno-political violence has brought on the lives of the people of Karachi. An attempt was made at understanding why people chose to bear the brunt of the happenings that have so distorted their daily routines. Various anthropological techniques have been used in the research which include socio economic surveys, in-depth interviews and participant observation along with sampling. The study includes an understanding of how different people react towards ethno-political violence and how it has, directly or indirectly influenced their lives and how they choose to deal with it along with focusing on the changes this type of violence has brought to their surroundings.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Every day, the citizens of Karachi wake up to a day filled with uncertainties, a day that could either end in political violence or happenings that could be linked to some form of ethnic hatred – basically a day with any possible outcome. At times when these acts of violence lead to the city completely shutting down within a matter of minutes and then too, no one seems to question this colossal closure.

Being part of a metropolis that contributes a considerable amount to the total revenue of our economy (Ahmed, 2012), I find it rather interesting that people of this city manage to get through the impacts of political violence and ethnic hatred that affect their daily lives so much without questioning the authority or showing any signs of non-compliance day in and out. Now, the authority that I tend to talk on here is not the state but the political authorities that reign over Karachi. One of these political establishments is deeply rooted in the city with its branches extending towards all aspects of social and political life. Be it a shop owner or a common housewife or an entire organization functioning in the city, the impact of the happenings taking place within this metropolis has left none untouched.

When people go out for office work, studies or even grocery shopping, no one is certain if they are going to reach home safely. When people turn on their televisions or listen to their radio or browsing through text messages, deep down, they almost always experience a feeling of uneasiness, like they will come across some bad news that will affect the security situation even further. It is also interesting to note that the lack of predictability that lingers around the lives of the citizens of Karachi plays an important role in determining their submissiveness towards the exploiting of sources.

How does the prevailing security situation affect the daily lives of the working people? What makes them so ardent on carrying on with their daily activities despite the threat of extortion and robbery and the like? How does the working of a particular political party influence the mere housewife or student? How does the

common man deal with such uncertainties on a daily basis? And more importantly, why do these events of ethno-political violence take place on such a large scale and what causes people to become so violent?

These are the very questions that need to be answered and for my thesis, I will be looking into the lives of those affected by the frequent events of ethno-political violence that takes place in Karachi. Also, I will be looking into the coping mechanisms that people of Karachi adhere to in order to survive their daily routines. The state interferes apparently in the matters of those who initiate and support these acts that leave the city paralyzed – sometimes for days.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Our understanding of the word violence leads us to believe that it is some sort of act that causes harm to other people or things. Basically, we can associate an act with violence if it results in damage of life or situations that affect the mental health of the sufferers. Acts of violence associated with some sort of political movement or party is usually referred to as political violence like the burning of vehicles upon arrests of a political worker or a shooting taking place that includes people associated with political groups etc. In Karachi, these political parties stem typically from some sort of ethnic solidarity that creates conformity among its members. This ethnic solidarity may be due to lingual, cultural or historical similarities that exist between the members of the political parties or due to subjugation and assault. When it comes to ethno-political violence and everyday life, the acts of violence occurring in the city of Karachi have a considerable effect on different spheres of everyday life. Every day, thousands of people roam the city, risking their safety for their work, education or upkeep of relationships. When people go out of their homes, be it a student, a teacher, an employee or an employer, they are all aware of the fact that there is always a probability that they can be subject to political violence at any given instant. This is the fear that lingers among people in all spheres. Be it the institute of marriage, the practice of child-

rearing, educational and moral values, and relationships of any kind, almost everything is affected by the ethno-political violence that prevails in the city.

Karachi's agony, at a reductionist level, though quite pervasive, is basically a conflictive relationship among a few powerful and highly ambitious individuals. Their use, inflammatory symbols including nationalism, religion and ethnicity, and the misuse of power by the official functionaries motivated by personal interests have not allowed any durable peace in the city.

(Malik, 1998)

Political violence is not a new term for the citizens of Karachi especially when it is linked to ethnic clashes and when combined, this ethno-political violence makes lives miserable all over the city, regardless of age and gender.

‘Ethno-political tensions lie at the heart of Sindh capital Karachi’s high levels of violence. With demographics rapidly transforming its ethnic landscape, political competition has become increasingly violent, as criminal gangs exploit their links to competing, largely ethnic-based parties.’

(Group, 2014)

Anyone who is living in Karachi knows exactly how difficult it is to get through the day without having to listen to some bad news. People of this city strive through their daily routine to carry on with their lives. Thus, the impacts that these events of ethno-political violence leave on the citizens, need to be studied with special emphasis on how people tend to react towards these events along with the coping mechanisms that they use. Their steady pace of compliance towards the political parties and the amount of fragility that is displayed by the state is something that requires a much closer analysis. Thus, my research is based on the ethno-political violence and everyday life.

1.2. Objectives

1. To study the effects of ethno-political violence on the lives of residents of Karachi
2. To study the coping mechanisms that the people of Karachi use to deal with ethno-political violence.

1.3. Significance of Study

The term ethno-political violence is actually very deeply rooted in Karachi, effecting millions of people citywide on almost a regular basis. What is interesting is the fact that it has, directly and indirectly, influenced lives in every corner of the city. People of this city have lived with ethno-political violence and the issues pertaining to it for more than three decades now, surviving personal, professional and psychological setbacks every now and then. The reason why studying the impacts of ethno-political violence on everyday lives of the residents of Karachi is so significant is because people have actually learned to live with it. They have internalized the events of ethno-political violence and their effects on their daily lives, learning to adapt to the security situation that has long persisted in Karachi. Since these events have a direct impact on these people, they have somehow managed to cope with the repercussions of having to worry about their security almost all the time. The research on the impacts of ethno-political violence on the daily lives of the people living in a prominent area and how they tend to deal with on a regular basis will provide an insight on the needs and requirements of the people who are practically deprived of the so-called peace of mind. It will also help the researcher understand why so many people or rather all of them choose to internalize the effects of ethno-political violence instead of standing up to and searching for a solution. This study will also indicate why people tend to stay quiet and adapt to the situation instead of speaking up and challenging the authorities along with providing a closer look to the ways in which they have chosen to adapt to the prevailing situation.

2. Background of Ethno-political Violence in Karachi

The prime reason behind the social unrest present in the city of Karachi can be indentified as the existence of a rather complex nature of the landscape of ethnic based politics. When looking at the history written about Karachi, one can come across the fact that the ethnic conflicts among *Sindhis* and *Mohajirs* began shortly after the initial migration from the neighboring India. The property of the Hindus that was left behind after evacuation, the issue of settlement and competition existing inside the Muslim League for dominant positions remained the main contention points. The property of the evacuees was to be distributed by the the Muslim League as it had arisen as the actual Pakistani state.

Sindh's socio-political progression was altered by the partition. Before the partition took place, the urban and middle class of Sindh comprised of Hindus. An urbanized and middleclass vacuum was left after their migration in 1947 to India in the province. The remaining classes comprising of feudal lords and peasants formed the *Sindhi* post partition society. Problems stated to emerge when the division of leadership took place on ethnic lines of the sole political party, i.e. the *Mohajir* elders versus *Sindhi waderas*, particularly the intellectuals and the religious leaders. However, in Karachi, the Muslim League was sucessfully dominated by the *Mohajirs* during the ealy independence years although they began brainstorming on the idea of a separate organization in Hyderabad. The initial *Mohajir* organization came to being in Hyderabad through a *hafiz* (someone who has memorized the entire Quran) who was blind and hailed from Jaipur, known as Mubarak Ali Shah. However, the *Jamiat-ul-Mohajirin* were still part of the politics in Sindh over which Ayub Khoro, the province's first chief minister expressed displeasure over the formation of groups like these which was illustrated through his speech of 1954 in which he explained that the formation of political, social and sectarian organizations has led to antagonizing of old *Sindhis*, especially when it comes to new setters. The ethnic messages favoring ethnocentrism continued gaining popularity in squatter areas

that were dominated by *Mohajir* residents in Karachi along with the neighborhoods of Latifabad and Pakka Qilla in Hyderabad. Consciousness of the *Mohajir Qaum* was crystallized as universities aided in providing a platform for it during the seventies.

In 1972, riots based on language issues and policies broke out when *Sindhi* was declared as the official provincial language, leading to it becoming a compulsory college and school subject. This move by the government was resisted by the *Mohajirs* as they took to the streets. After two years, the University of Karachi introduced the semester system and the “Intermediate Students Action Committee” was raised by around twenty seven students who were not able to get admission in order to get mid-term admission. The president was Altaf Hussain and the vice chancellor resigned as students were admitted without turn. The success of this committee provided the *Mohajir* students with a boost and on the eleventh of June, in 1978, the *Mohajir* students created their All Pakistan *Mohajir* Students Organization (APMSO). Now, some argue that the formation of the APMSO was rather an issue of addressing the apparent grievances of the *Mohajirs* in terms of the failure of fulfilment of promises by the leaders of the Pakistan National Alliance (PNA) in eliminating the quota system along with safeguarding of *Mohajir* lives against violence and tyranny. When it comes to the ethnic question, Moonis Ahmar, a professor at the University of Karachi says that the *Mohajirs*, during Zia’s rule, had increased their identity search along with the mobilization of ranks associated with them along the lines of ethnicity which was only a matter of time. The political and economic sense of deprivation had reached its zenith within this time and enough reasons to raise the nationalism slogan by the mid-1980s, promoting the one party and one leader unity of the *Mohajirs*. The APMSO was formed to fight for the rights of the young *Mohajirs* by mobilizing them. Then, the formation of the MQM came six days after the further ten-year extension of the quota (rural-urban) system in 1985 in the month of March. Altaf Hussain, in the August of 1986, vowed as the chief of MQM to unite *Mohajirs* and launch a movement for the attainment of their community rights under the MQM’s banner.

Karachi's volatile history is tainted with ethnic rioting. Some look at it as a part of the natural urbanization within a city deprived of proper planning. Thus, in an atmosphere where various communities belonging to different ethnicities tended to stay together in ghettos, violence resulted due to the need for holding onto a place to reside. The Urdu-speaking migrants dominated MQM set a platform in order to the *Pashtuns* who control the construction and transportation fields within Karachi.

The initial riots based on language, i.e. the *Pashtuns* versus the Urdu-speaking started in 1965 post elections. In 1972-73, seven years later, the Hyderabad and Karachi based *Mohajirs* clashed with *Sindhis*. Fresh riots broke out again in 1986 in April and October-December gripping Karachi for a period of two years – the Bihari migrants were attacked in Liaquatabad and Orangi by *Pashtuns* and the communities were avenged by the MQM. After two years, in the September of 1998 and the May of 1990, *Sindhis* and *Mohajirs* clashed for the second time. In the former month, around two hundred people were killed on a Black Friday in Hyderabad and Karachi. *Sindhi* and MQM nationalists attacked the strongholds of the opposite party when the MQM renamed Haider Chowk, replacing the centrally located area with posters depicting *Mohajir* heroes. The people of Hyderabad remember the 1990s (the last five years) as the war years. The freshly created MQM (*Haqiqi*) during these years also emerged leading to the eruption of violence between the break-away faction and the MQM. After the incident of 12th May, 2007, the eruptions of violence had ceased. The ill-fated day resulted in the deaths of around forty-eight individuals including *Pashtuns*, PPP activists, and *Mohajirs* along with the police. Alarm bells started ringing for the MQM when the ANP won two spots in the Sindh Provincial Assembly in the elections of 2008 for the very first time in history. This gave way to a wave of ethno-political violence that has grappled the city of Karachi for many years now. As the number of migrants and supporters of the ANP increase, so does the MQM's fear of losing power in its prized city.

3. RESEARCH

The following research is based on the effects of ethno-political violence on the daily lives of the people of Karachi with a focus on the residents of Block 2 of Pakistan Employees Cooperative Housing Society (PECHS).

4. LOCALE

The locale chosen for the purpose of the research is the Pakistan Employees Cooperative Housing Society (PECHS), Karachi because of the fact that it comprises of a multitude of ethnicities including *Mohajirs, Sindhis, Punjabis, Memons, Bohras, Ismailis, Kashmiris, Pashtuns, Baloch, and Seraikis*. Also, PECHS is linked to the city center as block #6 of the area goes through the main *Shahra e Faisal* which is known as the city center of Karachi. The area is also an active place for trade with multiple schools and colleges and markets available in nearby vicinities. The researcher's research was conducted in block #2 and the reason this locale was chosen is because since there are a lot of ethnicities present in the area along with people coming from different economic backgrounds, it was good area to get the required information for the researcher, i.e. people regularly commute here from other parts of the city for employment, shopping and recreational purposes and can provide ample data for understanding the effects of ethno-political violence on everyday life. Also, the different ethnic backgrounds were able to provide their views and experiences to help the researcher understand the research topic better along with gaining useful interaction.

Figure 2. Map of Karachi

Source: Google Maps

Figure 1. Map of PECHS

Source: Google Maps

Figure 3. Map of PECHS Block # 2

Source: Google Maps

As seen in the above map, the area includes a number of places of socialization for people including one of the most famous markets of the city called Tariq Road and parks used for leisure activities by people of almost all ages along with multiple schools and colleges, thus making access to respondents easier for the researcher.

4.1. Area Profile

Since the area of the research comprises of different types of ethnic communities and is an active area for people to socialize from all over the city, it is important to have a good understanding of how people function in their daily lives within their vicinity and what are their surroundings like, i.e. how far they tend to affect the lives of the people residing there. The area of the research includes people belonging from many ethnic backgrounds and these people interact with each other on almost a daily basis and are also somewhat equally affected by the events of ethno-political violence that take place in the city, although the people who actually partake in these events are more likely to cause damage than to suffer as they are

politically backed individuals having a strong attachment to their ethnic and political values.

4.1.2. Surroundings

PECHS Block #2 is an adequately populated area with a lot of things going on in the surroundings. Like many other areas of the city, the area of the research also comprises of shops and vendors located closely to the residential area. You don't have to go too far to buy groceries or visit the tailor or beauticians. Almost everything is located within walking distance of the houses. There are lush green trees at minimal distance from each other. Traffic is minimum, although it is never too quiet. There is a local park in the vicinity known as the *Jheel* Park allocated to the area residents for recreational purposes although only a handful of people are seen enjoying its perks. The people living there are hardly social with their neighbors and everyone actually follows the 'mind your own business' saying, never interfering in their neighbors' matters or socializing with them without any real purpose like at the time of a religious festival or weddings etc.

4.1.3. Ethno-political Groups

Although there are multiple ethno-political groups functioning in Karachi, at present, there are two groups that actually have more influence in the area of the research compared to others. These groups include the MQM (Mutahidda Qaumi Movement) comprising of a majority of and working for the rights of *Mohajirs* in the city and the ANP (Awami National Party) working for the rights of the *Pashtun* community in Karachi. Throughout the years, the migration of the *Pahstuns* from Afghanistan and Northern Areas – due to the ongoing security situations in these areas – to Karachi has led to a shift in the balance of power or to be more precise, there is a kind of visible rift going on between the ANP and the MQM for the acquisition of more land and more revenue in the city. Since the city is an active growing region for economic prosperity, more and more people tend to be associated with

ethno-political parties in order to secure their fair share of the wealth. Another political party functioning in the area, although not so influential, is the PPP. Though a lot of supporters of this party reside in the area of research, they seldom partake in anything violent as they are not actually part of the actual political movement and just tend to be watching things from a far. How workers of this party take part in the events of ethno-political violence across the city is another story.

4.1.4. Group Interactions

When profiling the area of the research, the researcher found that when it comes to group interactions, people hardly take part in socializing in the area. This of course refers to the residents that are not associated with the ethno-political parties functioning in the area. When someone wants to or has to organize an event within the area, they have to be careful as members of political party are always present in the neighborhood. This is because people know that there is a kind of stigma attached with political workers be it at ground level or above. You never know when a political worker will show up asking for food or some other thing at your event. Most of the ethno-political groups usually hang out at the park or adjacent to it in narrow streets where there is hardly any light after sunset. These are typically young men that tend to hang out with each other along with their motorbikes which they use to get around the area when there is a strike or something and discuss mundane things, smoking and sometimes even drinking for fun. People are actually reluctant to spend quality time in the park most of the time. The ones who are present are just young boys playing cricket and that too on the farther side of the park away from the street side as it usually features young men belonging to the MQM whereas the ones playing cricket are mostly Pashtun boys who work in the nearby commercial area. The people who wish to take a walk in the park or spend quality time in the park also tend to avoid going near the area where these young men can be found – mostly because people fear them and do not wish to get acquainted with them no matter what.

4.1.5. Barriers

Barriers are quite a common sight in Karachi. A lot of residential areas have barriers in place in order to make their area of residence more secure as acts of ethno-political violence take place at the spur of the moment and then not much can be done besides seeking refuge at home. The area of the research also featured a lot of barriers which were a security measure as stated by the residents. Since acts of shooting and driving by or barging in inside the residential areas is quite common in the city, the residents of the community usually agree to the installation of barriers for their own safety. Although it may lead to a bit of inconvenience at times, barriers have played an active role in making the people of PECHS Block 2 feel safer. Also, since there are a few high profile residents in the area, they are also the ones who were first to install these barriers to deal with their insecurity. The barriers also play an important part in creating spaces between the people as it separates the ones liable to events of ethno-political violence from the ones who are not. Thus, we can say that urban spaces, in a way, are themselves creating violence and conflict in the city by representing people's influence.

4.1.6. Belief Systems and Perspectives

During the research, the researcher came across an interesting fact pertaining to the belief systems of the ethno-political groups in Karachi and especially in the area where the research was conducted. Almost every individual associated with the ethno-political group viewed ethno-political violence as something that is rather a justified thing. They believed that in order to survive in this city and in order to obtain actual freedom, they need to defend themselves through instilling fear among others. When people will fear them, acquiring rights to land, resources and accumulation of power becomes significantly easier than just waiting for things to happen the democratic way. Since each group views itself as the marginalized one, resorting to ethno-political violence seems the logical thing to do, at least for the ones who believe that this is the *only* way. Although, when it comes to the common

people or the bystanders of ethno-political violence in Karachi, it is just something rather tedious and unnecessary – something which needs to end at any cost.

4.1.7. Banners and Mediums of Propagation

While conducting research in the area, it was also found that the ethno-political parties functioning within the vicinity also make active use of political banners and wall chalking in order to propagate their agendas. This can be witnessed on the walls of the roads that connect the residential streets to the commercial area. Also, graffiti can be seen on houses that are left empty.

4.1.8. Empty Houses

Another interesting phenomenon seen in the area of the research is the amount of empty houses currently present within the area. Most of these houses belong to residents who have shifted to another locality of the city while others of individuals gone abroad and the main reason for the presence of these empty houses was that their residents feared for their safety and thus left have their homes. Most of these houses tend to be sold or belong to tenants.

5. METHODOLOGY

Each scientific discipline comprises of its set of procedures and rules that need to be followed in order to conduct an effective research. Research methodology includes various techniques of research that can be used for data collection and the discipline of Anthropology consists of numerous instruments required to conduct a research. However, Anthropology allows the use of a unique approach for the collection of data making it rather diverse in comparison to other disciplines due to the fact that it features participant observation.

Fieldwork projects in anthropology are not what they used to be – at least as they have been imagined in an aesthetics of practice and evaluation that define anthropology’s highly distinctive disciplinary culture of both method and career-making....Indeed, accounts of fieldwork within ethnographies constitute a primary form of evidence for arguments, and often **are** the primary form of argument.

(James D. Faubion, 2009)

Thus, following are the anthropological techniques, methods and their applications that have been used in my research.

5.1. Rapport Building

With a population exceeding 23 million since 2014 (Karachi Population , 2015), the city bustling with people moving in from all parts of the country. Also, given the reputation it has of incidents of criminal activities and muggings taking place on a daily basis, it is also important to focus on proper rapport building prior to beginning any research. For an anthropologist conducting fieldwork, the first and foremost step to take is building rapport. During this step, the anthropologist starts building friendly relations with the respondents, trying to make them feel comfortable, so that their activities can be observed and interviews can be conducted without hassle. Besides, the researcher in this case was a native to the area and the people were

somewhat familiar with her. Although, there were few individuals who were quite reluctant to open up to the researcher as they kept wondering why someone would want to delve in such a topic that mostly brought despair and fear among the people especially when the researcher was away completing her postgraduate studies. This was also due to the fact that the situation in Karachi always tends to be kind of unstable and people usually look at others in a rather dubious way. Eyebrows were raised at more than a few instances when the researcher started asking questions around the neighborhood. Part of the reason why rapport building was smooth in this research is because the researcher knew her way around the neighborhood due to the fact that she was born in the very city and was able to communicate and understand – to some level – how people feel about being questioned and observed by strangers or about being asked questions that were rather politically sensitive in nature.

As the researcher started meeting people and talking to them, she was able to get her message through to them, i.e. make them understand the importance of her research and how her respondents would play a vital role in helping her recognize the role that ethno-political violence plays in the lives of the people living in PECHS on a daily basis and how they tend to deal with its repercussions. Being familiar with the dimensions of the area came quite handy here for the researcher. The researcher moved about in homes and offices and shops telling people about her motives and they seemed reluctant to participate at first but began to warm up soon after – when the purpose of the research and their part was explained to them. The researcher initially began discussing the daily events in the lives of Karachiites and slowly began descending deeper into the depths of the unusual events that took place in the area, i.e. the events of ethno-political violence and how it has affected many people citywide in various ways. As they heard these stories and experiences, they began to warm up to the researcher, eventually citing their own versions of the impact that ethno-political violence has left on their daily lives and how they tend to deal with it.

5.2. Key Informants

Key informants form a major part of the researcher's sources of information especially when it comes to information associated with various institutions present within an area.

According to Bernard,

'Good key informants are people whom you can talk to easily, who understand the information you need, and who are glad to give it to you or get it for you.' (Bernard, 2006)

The selection of the key informants is quite imperative when it comes to research and so the researcher chose the key informant on the basis of having sound knowledge of the area and the people who would be useful to the research, being a responsible and experienced individual and indulgence in matters or events associated with ethno-political violence. Thus, the researcher chose two key informants who were quite beneficial for the research. Among these the first one was a journalist working for a prominent newspaper that was distributed nationwide, hence having a good grip on the events of ethno-political violence that took place in the area and the news that it did or did not make. Since he had been writing for the national newspaper for quite a long time, he was able to provide ample information about people who would be helpful in forwarding the research. This informant introduced the researcher to many individuals who were directly affected by ethno-political violence in the area and how they had managed to cope with the ongoing situation in the city on a daily basis. Also, it was through this key informant that the researcher was also able to interview a member of the senate assembly. The second key informant was a rather different character from the first one as he was a *chowkidar* (watchman) working in the area of the researcher since before she was born. Thus, he was familiar with the area on an extraordinary basis and knew who lived where and who suffered through what. The second informant was also quite useful in providing the researcher with a good amount of the required

information leading her to rather unexpected respondents like shopkeepers and other watchmen working in the area.

5.3. Participant Observation

The researcher used the tool of participant observation in such a way that she thoroughly observed the feelings of the people while they told her about their views and experiences regarding the events of ethno-political violence that took place almost on a daily basis. The use of this tool became quite handy as the researcher was a native to the area. This helped the researcher understand the value system that exists among the people of the area, i.e. how they coped with the ongoing situations of ethno-political violence that have persisted in the area for decades now. Also, being a native provided a perk of being able to see through the thoughts and feelings of the respondents, knowing if the data is actually accurate or just exaggerated (this is an important factor because the area of the research was a place where ethno-political violence did not usually take place at front though the people living here bore the direct consequences of the events that took place around the city). The researcher tried to look into the words spoken by respondents, analyzing their gestures and how they reacted towards specific questions along with the way they behaved when asked about their opinions regarding ethno-political violence and how it has affected their daily lives. There were instances when the researcher was told to go away or return home immediately because the city was about to shut down. The researcher of course, had to comply in order to ensure personal safety. People would close their doors and sometimes were quite resilient towards opening up even to the ones they knew personally because they were accompanied by the researcher – someone who was unknown to them. The researcher thus documented the activities of the people and their experiences and views regarding the topic. Basically, participant observation helped the researcher notice and clearly see the real picture, extracting meaning from expressions, words and views of the people – studying closely the things that the respondents tried to hide

or were not able to discuss freely. This way, the researcher was able to observe a reality that was previously inaccessible to her.

5.4. Sampling

Sampling is quite crucial to any anthropological research as it provides reliability and significance to the data. It is not possible to document the opinion of all the people and so sampling provides the researcher with the opportunity to come in contact with those that can allow the extraction of considerable amount of data. The population of the area is divided into multiple strata based mainly on ethnicities and political allegiance. The sampling technique used in this research is a combination of stratified and snowball sampling. The reason the researcher chose stratified sampling is because the researcher wanted to include people from all spheres of life (working people, housewives, children, and people of different ethnicities) as her research is focused on ethno-political violence, getting the views of these people seemed the right way to do so. This included the division of people into strata of male and female and different ethnicities. Thus, this technique helped the researcher identify the important respondents in different spheres of daily life. The researcher also made use of snowball sampling as the key informants led her to people who were quite useful to the research, providing her with ample intel regarding the topic. Also, the target population were aware of the ethno-political situation in the city and cited ethno-political violence as something very ordinary and the majority of them were somewhat directly influenced by the events of ethno-political violence taking place within the area.

After coming across a number of individuals, the researcher was able to question a total of 62 respondents from which 48 were chosen for inclusion of data in accordance to the relevance of the information that was provided to the researcher. Among these respondents, 19 were single and 29 were married.

Table 1. Gender Data

Male	Female	Total
26	22	48

Source: Field data

Table 2. Ethnic Data

Ethnicity	Respondents
Urdu-speaking	9
Baloch	9
Punjabi	6
Sindhi	5
Pashtun	5
Memon	4
Khoja	3
Kashmiri	3
Ismaili	2
Bohras	2

Source: Field data

Since the researcher's research was based on the effects of ethno-political violence on everyday life, I thought it would be better to include as many ethnicities as possible in order to get an overall view of all.

5.5. Interviews

The interviews were the prime source for documenting the respondents' points of view. In order to do this, the researcher conducted both formal and informal interviews. The interviewing technique that the researcher chose for this research is the in-depth interviewing method or un-structured method of interviewing. The reason this technique was chosen is because there are a lot of things that need to be uncovered and issues that require active listening and in-depth questioning. People of Karachi have long been dealing with the issue of political violence and they need appropriate time to vent themselves, i.e. their issues, their requirements and their coping techniques. The researcher conducted formal interviews with the help of a questionnaire. These formal interviews included people who were ready to provide information accordingly and made it easier to create a flow whereas the informal interviews were conducted with people who were reluctant at providing information at first but later warmed up to the researcher in the course of the conversation. Thus, informal interviews allow the questions to be framed in the course of the conversation. Informal interviews are especially useful in gatherings where people have limited time and tend to answer rather casually. Most of the respondents felt burdened by the questions when they saw long questionnaires hence it was easier to maintain a conversational flow with informal interviewing in some cases. One thing that the researcher came across was the fact that people in formal settings were not able to answer properly and were unable to adjust to the surroundings at the time – this was mainly due to the presence of other people as well as the fear of being prosecuted for having 'different' views about a particular political party. Thus, informal interviews led to their answering the researcher deliberately and more openly. Probing was also used in the interviewing phase. Among the persons interviewed by the researcher, 18 were interviewed formally

and the rest were interviewed in an informal style. Also, the format of the questionnaire was mixed as part of the researcher's attempt to bring out valid results as the city of Karachi is filled with people coming from different ethnic backgrounds and statuses and thus will respond to questions differently – the researcher interviewed people from different spheres of life so this type of format came in handy.

6. LITERATURE REVIEW

In order to understand ethno-political violence, one must understand what political violence is. Basically, political violence is a type of violence that is mainly associated with political motives. People resort to political violence as a means of fulfilling their agendas, especially when it comes to creating a powerful impact on the residents of a particular area, creating a sort of a movement that leads to political success in the long run. According to O'Neil,

Political violence is violence outside of state control that is politically motivated. Some political scientists see political violence as part of “contentious politics” or collective political struggle, which includes such things as revolutions, civil war, riots and strikes, but also more peaceful protest movements. Crime and warfare share some attributes with political violence, but political scientists do not define them as political violence.

(O'Neil, 2011)

There can be various reasons behind the incursion of political violence. When looked at closely, one can easily see why these incidents of political violence actually take place. The most common reasons behind the occurrences of the acts of political violence is a difference of economic statuses, ethnic identities and a rule of governance that does not fit into the needs and requirements of the people – hence they resort to acts of violence to prove their point or bring about the required change or attract the attention of the people in power along with the masses. According to Mousseau,

In analyzing domestic political violence, most empirical cross-national studies hypothesize and test the existence of ethnic heterogeneity, autocratic governance, and economic under- development (or peripheral status in the

world system) as contributory factors to the occurrence of political violence within nations (Boswell & Dixon, 1990; Brown & Boswell, 1997; Hibbs, 1973; Muller, 1985; Muller & Seligson, 1987; Schock, 1996; Sigelman & Simpson, 1977; Weede, 1981).

(Mousseau, 2001)

When political violence involves the presence of ethnic identity or ethnic backing, it is termed as ethno-political violence or conflict. Ethno-political violence usually takes place between communities or groups of people hailing from different ethnic backgrounds supporting agendas that represent the needs of their particular ethnicity along with the support of some political party or movement. When an ethnic group feels unsupported or forced to live like they have no needs or they lack the ability to move forward economically and socially then it is more likely for that group to resort to some form of violence in order to draw the attention of the government or the citizens of their state towards their issues, i.e. to tell others how they are being marginalized or undermined by the state. Examples of politically motivated ethnic violence can be found all around the globe, such as the ever existing conflict between Palestinian Arabs and the Israeli Jews in Israel or the Tamils and the Sinhalese or the *Pashtuns* and the *Mohajirs* in Karachi. And since everyone sees themselves as victims, there are lesser chances of the issues being resolved through peaceful means. For instance, the *Mohajir* community backed MQM or Mutahidda Qaumi Movement in Karachi sees itself as a supporter of the marginalized *Mohajirs* in Sindh who are deprived of social and economic benefits in the society.

Conflict between two or more groups is termed “ethnopolitical” when ethnicity and religion are highly implicated in the ongoing state of hostility. These are intergroup conflicts where group member attitudes, stereotypes, and forms of communication reflect the ethnopolitical context. Group members interact with one another on the basis of social categories (e.g., Israeli Jew versus

Palestinian Arab; Northern Ireland Catholic versus Protestant; Hutu versus Tutsi; Sinhalese versus Tamil) and issues of identity, religion, and nationality are salient.

Also,

Ethnopolitical conflicts are particularly resistant to resolution because they are less subject to rational negotiation and more influenced by issues of deep personal identity, inviolability of space considered holy or sanctified, and psychological issues related to historical injustice, group vulnerability, and victimhood.

(Ellis)

Ethno-political violence usually takes place for a number of reasons. As mentioned before, the reasons might be political, economic or social although in a number of cases, the economic reason can be seen as the main cause. Since people are deprived of basic facilities, as in the case of the people associated with political parties in Karachi like the PPP, ANP, and the MQM, they tend to resort to ethno-political violence that tends to heed their woes – as these acts of ethno-political violence have a direct impact on the common man and his everyday life hence, affecting the state in one way or another. As Jourek explains,

There may be a number of reasons why ethnic conflicts arise: reaction of the ethnic groups to their discrimination or oppression; the dissatisfaction of an ethnic group with its status in the society, and so on. It is generally recognized that poor economic conditions are the major reasons for many contemporary ethnic demands. Although true in most cases, one should not simplify the problem by reducing it to a form of simple economic struggle. No matter how ethnic conflict manifests itself, there are usually several reasons underlying this conflict.

Ethnic conflicts pose a threat not only to international peace and stability, they are also a threat to the very countries involved in the conflict. Conflicts tend to divert the parties' attention, efforts, material and human resources from more important tasks. They create a nourishing environment for increasing the amount of crimes inside the countries, for developing extremism, even terrorism, for the violation of political as well as socio-economic human rights, etc., thus undermining the most important foundations of vitality of these states and occasionally leading to the complete disappearance of the states themselves.

(Jourek)

Ethno-political violence is quite common in the city of Karachi and owes much of its roots to the political parties that dominate the city – using it as a means of gaining power and support from their supporters. What political parties use for attracting allegiance from an ethnic group depends on what the target population thinks it is deprived of. For instance, in the case of the MQM, its supporters are mainly attracted through the manipulation of the *Mohajir* (a term typically used to label the Urdu speaking population in Karachi with its actual meaning being immigrant) emotion associated with alienation and deprivation of basic rights along with the feeling of being 'marginalized' by their surroundings. Thus, through ethnic identity, political parties aim at gaining power from the ones who can relate with them with the former promising better facilities and actually listening to what the people on ground really have to say about the issues that persist around them – linked to their ethnic values.

There can be several reasons accounting ethno-political violence that takes place within an area. Tarimo, while working in Kenya concluded that,

Politicization of ethnic identities appeals to the ethnic solidarity founded upon ties of blood-relationships as a model that can guarantee economic

security. This approach takes the form of a conservative return to the grassroots of ethnic identities. It appeals to cultural symbols in order to construct a sense of allegiance, which makes it easier to mobilize people. Sometimes they use cultural slogans to arouse emotions of the people in order to make them accept what they do not even understand. That is to say, interest groups competing for scarce economic resources tend to "invoke traditional sentiments to reinforce their appeal."

And,

When a person is in difficulties, it is normal for this person to call for help from the ethnic community to which he or she belongs. In urban areas ethnic identity is appealed to when people are in need of financial support and political support. For many people ethnic identity stands as a symbol of communal solidarity and security. Ethnic identity, be it in rural or urban areas, remains a powerful force to reckon with, although it varies like temperature, from time to time, depending on prevailing political circumstance.

(Tarimo, 2009)

If we emphasize on the situation in Karachi, its political conditions are no secret to the people of this country. The city reeks with ethno-political violence taking place every now and then among which targeted killings and disappearances are a common norm along with bouts of violent activities taking place here and there every time there is a political issue between the reigning political parties. Since the ones who participate in these acts of ethno-political violence are affiliated with strong political parties, they are seldom touched by the law for their doings. These are the very individuals who extort money from the residents of the city as a form of protection fee, i.e., if you pay, you stay safe or else there would be dire consequences. Often people are reported missing after they fail to comply with the threats of extortion. Basically, the seeds of ethno-political violence in Karachi sprout from the notion of economic power which of course leads to the attainment of

political power as well. When a political party has control over the resources of a metropolis like Karachi, it is bound to attain power which consequently leads to having the ability to influence the matters of the state and you can only control the resources when you have control over the people which becomes rather easy with the use of ethno-political violence, i.e., you tell people that you can protect you so that they can increase your vote bank, helping you control the city.

Karachi's history is evident of an obvious economic success mitigate by violent 'ethnic' and 'sectarian' quarrels. However, such classification is deeply challenging mainly because "Karachi's so-called 'ethnic' and 'sectarian' conflicts originally had little to do with ethnicity and religion. They were primarily 'urban struggles' between the opposing local groups for the control of the most affluent city in the country". These groups include different Mafias, land grabbers and criminals. They fight each other to grasp the control of different parts of the city. Many areas of the city have become 'no go areas' by these groups for rival groups. Residents of these areas are (reportedly) forced to pay ransom for the safety of their homes and businesses.

Karachi has been experiencing periodical and uncontrollable violence, being struck by cruel, targeted killings. The most preferential method has been the "drive-by shootings", where the killers, customarily remain untraced. "Incompatible political, sectarian and linguistic affiliations, marked by intense personal rivalries, are said to be a major cause of the blind murders".

(Ali, 2012)

Another interesting fact about this metropolis is that people who claim to fight for their ethnic rights and identity are readily involved in criminal acts and since these people are protected by their political beneficiaries when it comes to being convicted, they openly continue breaking the law. Violence thus erupts when gangs supported

by different political parties fight to reign and continue their criminal activities in a particular area.

Karachi has become a battleground for criminal gangs involved in racketeering, drugs, arms and human trafficking. Ethnic and political divisions fan the violence. Turf wars between the many gangs in Lyari, where the ethnic majority are Baluchs, often turn into ethnic clashes. (Khan, 2013)

Now, in terms of the people who are subject to ethno-political violence, there are countless effects of ethno-political violence that shape and mold the ones affected either directly or indirectly. Ethno-political violence generally affects people from all backgrounds regardless of color, gender and age. Although, some people are more susceptible to its effects compared to others. The former usually include people who have seen acts of ethno-political violence taking place up front and bearing the brunt of these incidents to a considerable amount. Of these, young minds are more likely to suffer as they are in the developing stages of life, forming their worldviews from their surroundings. Though adults may experience feelings of discontent for ethno-political violence, it is the younger individuals that actually suffer to a great extent both mentally and emotionally. There are times when people who have been subject to the events of ethno-political violence develop hatred towards the faction that hurt them, possibly shaping their entire lives same way, i.e., harboring regrets, aggression and distrust towards other ethnicities because they believe their future to be compromised. If we look at the work of Muldoon in Northern Ireland,

Young people from deprived backgrounds generally report greater experience of political violence than their middleclass counterparts, boys report more experience than girls and ethnic minority group members report more than those from the majority group. The net effect of these wider social factors

is crucial to a full understanding of the impact of conflict. Inequity of experiences may contribute to feelings of disempowerment and alienation in young people, particularly when issues such as equity and social justice are central to the conflict itself....young men feel alienated from institutions of social control....violence is seen as prevalent and pervasive in their communities and as an acceptable solution to many of their problems.

(Muldoon, 2004)

Ed Cairns and Andy Dawes in *Ethnic and Political Violence - A* also conclude that,

Given the terrifying experiences that some children are subjected to as a result of political violence, it is not surprising that some researchers have claimed that such children may develop representations of themselves and the future that are very limited if not overtly pessimistic (Cairns, 1996). For example, Roe (in press), as a result of his work with child evacuees in the Philippines and Central America, noted a marked lack of "futuraity."

(Dawes, 1996)

Over the years, Karachi has seen an extreme rise in the events of ethno-political violence taking place within the city. As the migration of the *Pashtuns* has increased from the north to the south of the country, so has the need for accommodation and the provision of economic and social security giving way an increase in violent activities in the city as other ethnicities or rather power factions fear the loss of revenue and land holdings ultimately leading to lesser vote banks. Naturally, this does not make the reigning parties of the city very happy. As Yusuf explains,

The ongoing stretch of violence in Karachi is significantly more complex and explosive than the situation in the 1980s and 1990s for several reasons. Previously, the armed militias of the MQM were the primary violent actors in the city. In the past decade, however, the demographic profile of Karachi has changed, owing to the steady migration of Pashtuns from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and FATA. These Pashtuns increasingly enjoy political representation through the Awami National Party (ANP). Karachi's Pashtun population has also benefited from the transportation boom triggered in 2001 by the supply of NATO goods from Karachi Port to Afghanistan. Their increased economic clout has allowed them to better organize and equip themselves to confront the armed wings of the MQM. Not surprisingly, a greater number of violent actors has worsened the security situation.

(Yusuf, 2012)

As people keep pouring in Karachi in search for employment opportunities and a better future, so does the need to provide these people with what they want. Political parties play a crucial role here, targeting the ones who feel deprived of basic rights and active socialization along with the resources to proper education. These run-down individuals are then rather easy to attract when it comes to forming militant factions as they are too desperate to resist anything that provides them with even the least bit of ease.

‘Devoid of education, employment, and entertainment, young Karachiites are prime targets for recruitment by the armed wings of political parties, criminal gangs, and militant organizations.’

(Yusuf, 2012)

When we look at the actual events of ethno-political violence taking place city, there are numerous ways in people tend to be affected. There is an intricate system

of functioning in the city of Karachi developed by its inhabitants over the decades. In contending the ones affected by ethno-political violence in Karachi, Tania Ahmad concludes that,

In Karachi's middle-class neighbourhoods that are conspicuously considered the turf or contested turf of political parties, tactics of standing by took multiple forms. During violent scuffles, these involved taking refuge and waiting until the worst was over before tentatively emerging to resume more ordinary routines. Where parents perceived a diffuse threat, locating violence in recruitment and affiliation, they grappled with everyday attempts to ply or admonish their children to remain in surveillable spaces. Other, often younger and unmarried Karachi residents resolved to be fearless, and saw no paradox in their confident negotiation of variously politicized friendships and activities that elided any particular party affiliation.

(Ahmad)

7. Daily Routine

During my research, I have come to understand that in order to understand the effects of ethno-political violence on everyday life, it is imperative to understand where this violence actually comes from or how it is rooted in Karachi so profoundly. According to my observation and the interviews that I conducted with my respondents, ethno-political violence basically began in Karachi when political parties realized that the best possible way of creating a vote bank is making sure that people are divided or in the words of one of my respondents, “it’s all a divide and rule strategy”.

Every party wants to be the last one standing within the metropolis as it guarantees their positions in power with the city actually being ignored by unconcerned provinces, the privileged class and the negligent state. Along with a sectarian conflict that is intensifying with each coming day, the city is now rooted with ethno-political violence. There are endless events of shootings, theft, and murders taking place in the middle of the day. Over the years, as the involvement of parties increased in the city, so has the occurrence of ethno-political violence. People with different ethnic backgrounds seek the help of these political parties in order to sustain a safe environment for their families and ensure their economic well-being as some agree that supporting a particular political party will keep them safe from harm. Thus, it all boils down to stronger vote banks. Acts of ethno-political violence are incited to increase political support through playing the ethnicity card because in Karachi, the root conflict lies in a struggle for elementary needs of the human being, like economic and political participation, security and disruptive justice. Here, feuding groups have managed to create a crack along ethnic lines that is complemented with eruptions of violence.

What is apparent is the fact that you can see how prevalent ethno-political violence and its fear is when you walk around the neighborhood of PECHS where you’ll find barricades at almost every street. And this is not only limited to the area of my research. Given the security conditions of the city, barricades are quite common.

These barricades provide the affluent neighborhood with the much needed security that it deems necessary.

It wouldn't be wrong to say that the events of ethno-political violence that take place on a frequent basis in Karachi have affected almost all of its residents in one way or another. The ones most affected with ethno-political violence are mainly people who earn wage on a daily basis and the youth. When an event of ethno-political violence takes place, people are forced to shut down their lives. This means that when the news of such an event spreads, the city literally freezes with shops being shut down, office and school/college goes hurry to their homes to be safe and vendors and shop owners bring their shutters down in order to avoid being told to do so. In many cases, when someone from a political party is killed or fired at, workers of that party hop on their motorcycles, circling around town to make sure that everything is shut down. If someone does not agree, they are treated with threats and sometimes, violence as well.

7.1. Case Study

Ahmed Yar Khan is a forty year old shop keeper from a *Pashtun* background who, when interviewed, showed constant resent towards ethno-political violence. Ahmed owns a grocery shop in PECHS Block 2 with a flourishing business. A lot of people tend to visit his shop which is conveniently located between streets that connect various houses along with having a link to the main market. Since his shop falls nearer to the residential area, he gets a lot of customers from all around the block. When expressing his views on ethno-political violence and how he sees it affecting his personal and business life on a daily basis, Ahmed explained how he lost his youngest son due to their belonging to the *Pashtun* ethnic background. He has been a witness to ethno-political violence when his son was shot in front of his eyes. This happened when his son refused to shut down their shop during a strike call by the MQM. He still grieves heavily and curses the ones who were responsible for his son's death, protesting that his son's death was not a mere

accident and that he will never be able to get over it. This is a mere example of how much people follow the word of the politicians who control the workers and incite violence for their own political gains. Though he has been living the city for almost all of his life and his sons also have been born here, the amount of frustration within the youth is clearly shown by his resilience in front of those bike riders even though he was fully aware of what happens upon non-compliance. Ahmed is one of the many people who believe his son was only shot down because they belonged to a different ethnicity.

7.2. Getting Around

On a day like this, travelling becomes extremely difficult, you can't use your own vehicles because you're afraid that it may be attacked or torched. If you decide upon renting a cab or rickshaw, you won't be able to find one and all because everyone is afraid for their lives. If we could sum the impacts of ethno-political lives on the people of Karachi in one word, it would be 'fear'. Almost everybody is afraid and uncertain of their longevity. One has to think twice before stepping out of their home in the event of an event of ethno-political violence and even when it is nightfall. Nobody knows when they will be the next target just because they belong to a particular political party or ethnicity. There are people whose relatives have been brutally murdered only because they were Baloch.

7.3. Case study

There were others who became victims of ethno-political violence only because they spoke *Pashto* and were not ready to corroborate with the workers of another political party. People lack the ability to travel freely to particular areas that are strongholds of the MQM, the PPP or the ANP because they know they will be treated differently due to their different ethnicity. Fear of life, fear of not being able to see their loved ones again, fear of being unable to see the next sunrise is something that is sort of built in the people of Karachi.

7.4. Case Study

Waheed, is a twenty year old student studying at the department of History at the University of Karachi pursuing his bachelors degree. He provided a different outlook on ethno-political violence and daily life in Karachi. Belonging to an Urdu-speaking background, Waheed joined the APMSO (All Pakistan *Mohajir* Student Organization – a subgroup of the MQM) only when his brother was killed during a strike call. Waheed belongs to a middle-class family and lives with his mother as his father passed away when he was younger. He had one sibling, i.e. a younger brother named Mudassir who died in an event of ethno-political violence. According to him, you can either join them or become their victims. Waheed's brother Mudassir was beaten for roaming about when people were warned not to come out of their houses during the mourning strike call of a MQM worker. He had to carry his brother to the hospital because there was no transport available. Thus, Waheed claims that being a part of that ethnicity did not exempt him from bearing loss, only becoming a part of it did. Now he studies at the university and hardly attends classes without being bothered for attendance (one of the perks of joining and working for the group).

Another youth named Ramish, also a 24 year old Urdu-speaking was murdered days before saying that the APMSO provides for his expenses and in the event of his death, will provide compensation for his family as well.

“set hojata hai banda bhai! Koi tension nai zameen mil jati hai ghar walon ko muafzay mein aur kya chahiye hain?”

According to Waheed, these were his last words before a rift evolved inside KU between the members of APMSO and Jamiat. Ramish was shot to death on campus. Waheed and Ramish were classfellows and members of the same group as they reaped benefits from joining the group. They both came from deprived backgrounds which made them easy targets for recruitment. Also, the APMSO provides admissions assistance to students who wish to support and join their group as the seats in the

University of Karachi are limited and provided on merit basis, this perk attracts many individuals wanting to study in a government university as it provides a subsidized fee structure and convenient degree programs. Students can choose from fifty two departments and various research facilities to pursue their careers in. Thus, people try very hard to get in and earn a degree which again is made possible once you join a student political wing like that of the APMSO or the Jamiat – both of these groups are reigning the student politics in the University of Karachi at present.

Ethno-political violence takes its toll on multiple spheres of daily routine when it comes to the people of Karachi. One cannot expect to see people of any sphere being excluded from its effects. The people who work on ground level are rarely thought to be affected by this type of violence as they are usually the ones considered to be having nothing to lose because mostly they own nothing extravagant or own any luxuries. What they earn is just a means of moving forward in life. However, the following case study presents a different version of the truth behind ground level influence of ethno-political violence in Karachi, especially in PECHS block # 2.

7.5. Case Study

Nasrullah, a thirty-something (he couldn't recall his actual age because of being born at home) *chowkidar* working in an apartment building explained how his fellow *Pashtuns* survive these bouts of ethno-political violence in the city. According to him, they have a close-knit network that allows them to operate their shops during shut downs within the vicinity of PECHS. His friends and fellow tribesmen from Waziristan came here when operations started and began working to earn for their families back home just like him. The Pashtuns coming from other parts of the country like Nasrullah, earn a living so that they can save money to go back and spend some quality time with their family. Nasrullah works in a three-storey apartment building functioning as a watchman. He works the day shift while the night shift is taken over by another colleague. He usually stays in Karachi for six months at a time, sometimes even longer, and saves up to buy things for his family

and spend the remaining money back home. His duties also include running the water motor and helping the residents with car parking and occasionally washes the cars parked in the parking area in order to receive some extra cash at times. When an event of ethno-political violence takes place, Nasrullah and his colleagues cum friends resort to seeking refuge to the local shops or apartments owned by fellow *Pashtuns* usually hailing from the same region. Also, since they have a sort of conformity among themselves, they can choose to stay put and face anyone who wishes to undermine them due to the support they have from the ANP. According to him, since they usually sleep on rooftops of the apartment buildings they are working at, they can easily get around during strike calls and manage their food requirements as well because the majority of the food and tea sellers are *Pashtuns* and they do not agree to strike calls announced by the MQM. They provide each other with protection and look after one another in need of space of filling in for the day at the shop. This is only possible because they are affiliated with the ANP.

8. Coping Mechanisms

Every day, millions of Karachiites come out of their homes to go to school/college, work, shop or run errands. Ethno-political violence has greatly affected how people view their daily lives. When people get out of their homes, they are afraid, they are anxious because they never know for sure whether or not they will be able to go back home safely. In offices, people tend to worry and sometimes even panic when they hear of an event of ethno-political violence taking place in the city. Even a text is enough to invoke havoc in offices. People get confused, start panicking and figure out ways of getting home before the city shuts down completely. Uncertainty has grappled people of Karachi over the years and so no one is willing to take any chances when it comes to their own safety.

8.1. Effect on the Daily Earners and Low Income People

Though office going people are afraid and can't afford missing out on work, it is the daily wage earners who suffer the most from this type of violence. Laborers, street vendors and the like are dependent on their daily earnings to provide for themselves and their families. Missing out on a day of work due to an event of ethno-political violence means having to give up on a day's wage that can help get food in for the day, buy stationary for the children or even medicine for a sick family member.

8.2. Case Study

Sheherbano is a thirty-five year old Kutchi Memon woman who works in houses in PECHS as a maid. Her main duties include cleaning and cooking in several houses during daytime and looking after her family of eight after work. Though she herself lives in Khokrapar (another violence ridden area in Karachi), she commutes to the area with other women who also work as maids and they travel together on a daily

basis, paying the van driver a monthly fee of 1500 PKR per person. When an event of ethno-political violence takes place, Sheherbano and her colleagues usually end up taking refuge by stopping at the nearest house of any fellow maid and if that is not possible, the van reroutes towards the safest exist without a minute to waste. Even though her area of residence is highly prone to the repercussions of any political violence taking place in the city, she still manages to show up at work almost every single day. That's because though she earns minimum salary, she can't afford to miss out on work as two of her three employers cut her pay every time she misses out on a day of work.

“teen hazar to mahina ka milta hai aur ek din na aun to baji 100 rupay kaat leti hyn. Ab gharib karay bhi to kya ap hi batao.” (Sheherbano).

There are many others like Sheherbano who simply lack the choice of missing out on a day's work because they depend so heavily on their incomes. Thus, even though they also fear for their safety, they are still courageous enough to face the everyday life ridden with insecurity and uncertainty.

8.3. Effect on Family Life

People are simply frustrated with this type of violence. They lack peace of mind and always fear the worst. When it comes to children, they seem rather tedious of what is going on their city. They can't go out and play like they used to because it is unsafe. Instead, they resort to the use of electronic gadgets for playful entertainment which is rather damaging for their physical and social wellbeing. Mothers seem discontent with their children developing weird allergies and getting specs but for them, it is better to have a child who is emotionally disruptive than no child at all. Although some of the children seem to deal with ethno-political violence rather swiftly, i.e. they just pretend nothing is wrong (as most people like to do in the city). We can say that they have become used to it or have become immune to it all (they have just adapted to the situation). However, if one observes carefully, there are children who have taken a fancy to this prevailing culture of

violence which is pretty evident from the fact that they would rather purchase toy guns than toy cars for play.

8.4. Case Study

Aysha, a Punjabi speaking woman in her late twenties belonging to an affluent background insists that although her husband is well off and her children study at schools with proper security, but she still fears that someday she will get a call from the police or hospital saying that one of them has been in “an accident”. Although she claims that this in fact is her paranoia talking, she can’t help herself.

“We’ve grown up watching this. You never know my dear....anything can happen...kabhi bhi kuch bhi ho sakta hai is shehar mein.”

Aysha also contends that she doesn’t let her kids play outside much even though she (as an educated woman) knows that it is rather necessary for kids to build immunities by interacting with the outside world. Her daughter Alizay, now 4 years old is not allowed to ride her bicycle outside of her home because her mother fears she will get hurt or be taken away from her for extortion.

This behavior is not limited to people like Aysha, another example would be that of Sughra Aziz, wife of the late Aziz Baloch who was attacked during the events of May 12th, 2007. Her husband was driving towards the sabzi mandi (vegetable market) as part of his business routine and was attacked by unknown personnel. His car was smashed with heavy rocks and he was thrashed on his steering wheel which lead to internal bleeding. Aziz died of brain hemorrhage the following night. Although the identity of the suspects was never known, Sughra believes that it was the workers of the MQM (which were also brandished as responsible by media and several important political personnel) as the area of the incident is regarded as a *Mohajir*-dominant area. However, the case still remains unresolved with the police not being able to catch the ones responsible (as so happens with the majority of ethno-political killings in Karachi).

Teachers also have a particular outlook on how children are affected through ethno-political violence as students who tend to have personally witnessed such an account go through considerable changes in personality and behavior.

8.5. Case study

Aneesa is a fifty-two year old widow working in a local school as a teacher, educating children from grades 5th to 10th in the course of Urdu. She belongs to the Khoja Shia community and lives with her mother and two kids, son and a daughter. Aneesa provided her outlook as an educationalist on the effects of ethno-political violence on the daily lives of children, i.e. how it is shaping their thoughts and their realities. She told me about one of her students whose name was Nasir. According to Aneesa, Nasir was a very good student studying in the fifth standard when he became the victim of the effects of ethno-political violence. Nasir suffered personal incident which led to his happy-go-lucky personality being changed into something that can be described as catatonic. The reason behind his sudden behavioral change was that his mother was shot in front of his eyes when she was driving him to school and was confronted by two men on a motorcycle demanding that she hand over her valuables. She didn't comply and was shot. This has left Nasir in a shock and now he barely smiles or hangs out with other children. Even though he receives counselling from the school guidance counselor and aid from his teachers, Aneesa does not think that he can ever come out of it and even if he does, he will never be the same.

8.6. Effect on Youth

The events of ethno-political violence have left a rather devastating effect on the youth of Karachi. Young men and women seem quite frustrated when it comes to going out with their friends or roaming about freely for a cup of tea. Now, youngsters belonging to a more elite class seem less frustrated though as they are

provided with ample security, but for the ones who can't afford this kind of luxury, transforming from young adolescences to adults becomes pretty difficult.

This can be explained with the example of Amir, a twenty eight year old Urdu-speaking man studying in KU, belonging to a middleclass background. Amir said,

“kahan jaye bhai banda? Raat ko chai pine ke liye bhi nai ja skate piche se ghar walay tang krte hayn sawal jawab krke, ‘kahan ho? Kab aoge wapas?’ tang hai banda fulltime aur kuch nahi bas bethe raho ke kab bari aayegi jane ki.”

According to this young man, he can't travel freely around the area even for a cup of tea with friends although the tea shop is near the Jheel park (as shown in the locale map).

Now, the amount of frustration among the youth is simply astounding. Even the doctors residing in the area agree that majority of the cases they get these days are associated with depression. Much of the youth the researcher came across show a particular kind of resilience when it came to ethno-political violence in the city.

They tend to harbor resentment and anger towards the people who are actually involved in these acts of ethno-political violence along with the government due to its lack of initiatives against the wrong doers and failing to provide them with the protection and surety of a prosperous future.

8.7. Case Study

Karim is a twenty-three year old student of Business Studies belonging from the Bohra community. Ethno-political violence has left a good amount of impact on his life in a way that he feels that he can deal with just about anything after years of watching and learning first hand. Karim recalled a time when he was driving to South City hospital to pick up his ailing mother and being stopped by MQM party workers on the way because they had announced a strike call. The strike call happened because of the murder of a prominent MQM leader residing in the United

Kingdom. Karim protested that his path was obstructed and he was thrown out of the car onto the ground. He remembers being covered in dirt and spraining his ankle. However, he was able to get back into his car and quickly drive away and returning to his mother. He never told his family about what had happened because he knows his mother will never let him travel alone again.

Students are also victims of ethno-political violence on a large scale in such a way that their schools and universities shut down, their papers get cancelled or postponed. People applying somewhere for further studies or awaiting results are thus forced to miss their admission deadlines.

8.8. Effect on Businessmen and Traders

Businessmen and shop owners face losses as well along with people who are involved in accidents and cannot reach the hospital in time because the roads are blocked. Countless lives are lost every year in Karachi due to this along with the actual killings taking place during the events of ethno-political violence. Businessmen are left with the obstacle of facing up to extortion which they cannot find a way out from. Industrialists and traders who do not wish to pay the protection money or Bhatta (in Karachiites terms) are forced to learn the risks of kidnapping, assassination or torture. A lot of them tend to end up being found in *boris* or sacks on the roadside after being murdered. Though there have been lockouts, protests and meetings, the administration has still not felt the heat of heeding a result only because of their affiliations with political parties that are actively involved in the affairs of the government. Also, as a result of the prevailing ethno-political violence, shop keepers and traders tend to close up rather early regardless of the losses it might bring except for holiday seasons when there is ample security provide to them during late hours by the government and fellow trader community members.

8.9. Case Study

As with the case of Mustafa, a 53 year old businessman belonging to the Bohra community. Though he has long been running a business in the city, he still can't get used to the idea of his community people being targeted every now and then. "We never bother anybody, we've always been a peaceful community and I just don't understand why they target us." The Ismailis have also been targeted in recent days, becoming victims of ethno-political and sectarian violence.

Ethno-political violence has left many scarred for life both in physical and non-physical ways. There were respondents who claim that this form of violence has made their life into something matching paralysis. People rarely go out to have fun now after late hours unless they are equipped with proper support, i.e. security guards.

9. LIVING WITH ETHNO-POLITICAL VIOLENCE

Interestingly, there are a range of coping mechanisms used by the people of Karachi to deal with the effects of ethno-political violence on their daily lives despite the fact that they are full of fear, anger and resent (against the state for being inactive, against the parties involved in these acts and against the people who support such parties). Some have chosen to deal with it quietly, becoming oblivious to what goes on, some are bruised and choose to keep their wounds fresh, some become resilient – habituating to the violence and some have just learned to incorporate it in their daily lives as something quite ordinary.

9.1. Case Study

Javeria is a thirty-four year old mother with a twelve-year old son. She is married to a businessman and they both belong to the Memon community. According to Javeria, she works at an insurance company profiling possible cases for insurance claims. Her husband works in the Karachi Metropolitan Corporation and their son studies at school currently finishing seventh grade. Upon deeper conversation, the researcher found out that Javeria struggles with keeping up with her daily routine regardless of the acts of ethno-political violence that go on in the city. Although she is not worried for her safety at a bigger scale or seems bothered with the safety of her husband, she cannot help but worry over the fact that her son chooses to play video games that contain a lot of violence and gory scenes. She believes that the reason her son chooses to buy such video games and play them with such addiction is that he has been born into a culture of where guns are seen everywhere possessing a gun and shooting someone to kill them does not seem such an ugly thing. She said that she hears sounds of gunfire and loud music while sitting in her lounge although her son's room is upstairs. Her son Afzal hardly displays any awkward behavior when talked to and provides the image of a youngster who has absorbed whatever goes around in his surroundings and is actually used to it to a good extent.

If you look carefully, you will see that all spheres of life are affected by ethno-political violence one way or another and since these spheres are linked to each other, a lot needs to be done in order to develop a way out of it. Ethno-political violence runs deep in the veins of Karachi and the further you dig, the messier it becomes. The city is becoming ungovernable as the violence in Karachi moves one step further towards triggering something ugly.

9.2. Cultural Repercussions

The cultural repercussions of the ethno-political violence taking place on a daily basis in Karachi are visible through the analysis of the behavior of the people residing in the apparently ethno-politically shielded area, i.e. the locale of the research. People tend to scurry around their destinations when they commute during the day and avoid travelling at night. Even though the shops and services are located in close vicinity, the residents of the locale prefer traveling by car unless they don't have one. Kids are confined to playing in the streets in front of their houses instead of going to the nearest park for recreational activities because it is not 'safe enough' and not allowed by their parents. When it comes to weddings, the brides tend to travel in shaded cars and when leaving the wedding venue, take off all their jewelry in order to avoid being robbed.

9.3. Case Study

Jawwad is thirty-four year old married man trying to run his own business. He has a small family and no children. His wife is a doctor and he frequently picks her up and drops her off when the driver is not available. Jawwad and his wife Sana (she shares the same age as her husband as well) are both Baloch and since they were born in the city and raised here, they know exactly how to behave when it comes to keeping themselves safe from bouts of ethno-political violence or from being subjected to other crimes like theft and extortion. When Jawwad and Sana

got married, they held their wedding reception at a posh location and remembered how insecure they felt regarding the safety of their guests at the reception. Also, when Sana was brought to the wedding hall after getting ready from the local parlor, i.e. after having her bridal makeup and jewelry put on, she was driven to the reception area in a car with tinted windows and newspaper attached to them. This was done to hide Sana completely from anyone driving by the car as events of on-road robbery are quite common in Karachi and can lead to a bloody mess when people fail to comply with what the thieves are demanding. Also when the reception was over, Sana had to take off all her jewelry and put in a purse for safe-keeping before exiting the reception hall. The same was the case with other female members of the family – they were all busy hiding their gold jewelry before going out to the car and heading home.

The fear and anxiety just keep escalating as days move on, especially when they are aware of the fact that ethno-political violence can take place at any time and any place.

There are stances when this fear is clearly displayed by the actions of the people. For instance, some of them believe that there are areas in Karachi which are actually much safer than others due to the presence of the ethno-political party stronghold. People of that area feel that they cannot be subject to violence because they are protected by the party workers' presence although they also believe that this limits their mobility as well. For instance, there are a lot of people in the locale who prefer not commuting to areas like Naizmabad and Orangi Town just because they are political strongholds. Likewise, if they belong to an Urdu-speaking background then going to a *Pashtun* stronghold is out of the question.

Living in a city where it is a common norm to deal with these bouts of violence, people have certainly adapted to their surroundings and continue to move on with their lives regardless of what goes on because they know that the state does not and will not help them in any way so it is literally every man for himself for

those who can provide security for their families do so and those who cannot rely on God's will to let them live another day.

10. CONCLUSION

Clearly, ethno-political violence has brought a significant change in the daily lives of the people of Karachi as almost every single respondent agreed that these events have brought some amount of change to their lives either directly or indirectly. A lot of people I interviewed agreed that it is not about ethnicity and more about political affiliation but their behavior showed that they still do believe in it, though on a smaller level. Also, the level of impact on the people also varies according to their economic status and employment levels though impact is present in one form or another. So, how involved are people in making the best of their lives while struggling through their daily life activities without being subject to the repercussions of ethno-political violence? The answer is very much. The majority of the respondents that were involved in my research agreed that they have not seen days when everything was normal and fearless. They just heard stories from their elders about the peaceful times that used to exist before the early eighties. After three decades, the city of Karachi still burns and echoes of the heinous crimes of political violence that take place every now and then. What is more is that anyone who wants to raise their voice against these notorious forces of violence is just 'dealt with' in the manner that one is even afraid to think.

Now, there is a common belief here that people living in areas like PECHS are less subject to the impacts of ethno-political violence than those living in areas like Nazimabad or Gulshan. However, this is seldom the case. Being an urban area, a megalopolis, Karachi is used to people travelling from one end to another in order to seek their daily wage, attain education or tend to businesses. The tradition of protection money also exists in areas like PECHS. One cannot travel alone to the gym nearby even if it is at walking distance due to the fear instilled among the hearts of the residents of this area. Even the local construction workers are frequently 'mugged' by policemen at different times during a single day because they seek

protection, protection for their lives which hardly costs anything to people who work for political parties that tend to get their 'work done' through ethno-political violence. The level of resilience is also astounding among the young and the old who have learned to 'just deal with it'. Since everything in their lives is interlinked either politically or socially, people have just learned to adapt just like the human beings have for millions of years, to their surroundings, to their situations and to the pain that they carry around with them each and every day, thus every day, they find new ways to survive and hope to make it through just so that their future generations may also do the same.

Socio-Economic Survey

Respondent	Age	Ethnicity	Profession	Marital Status	Education
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					

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